

National security and human rights: dialectics of interconnection

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Abstract. The article reveals the relationship between the problems of national security and the problem of human rights, world experience and the peculiarities of the national approach to solving the problem in Ukrainian society. It is shown that national security and human rights are organically interconnected, but the real interdependence of the phenomena of national security and human rights is often contradictory due to the division between the interests, values and goals of individuals and their associations, on the one hand, and the interests of large human communities of which they are a part, on the other. It is substantiated that the problem of interdependence of national security and human rights is a problem of compromise between ensuring national security and respect for human rights, between the realization of human rights and the protection of national security.

Ensuring the security of the individual, society and the state is today the most important goal of reforming the country. At the same time, the level of real protection of socio-economic, civil and political rights and freedoms of the individual is increasingly an indicator of the political stability of society and the state. Recognition and consolidation at the constitutional level of fundamental human and civil rights, constant expansion of their scope and clarity of formulation of their content, guarantees of their implementation are also, along with security, one of the most pressing and priority issues of modern civilization. That is why human rights are the normative and institutional context in which the conceptualization and practical provision of national security is carried out.

Moreover, the problems of security and human rights are correlated both in theory and in terms of manifestations in socio-political life. Human rights and freedoms are today one of the most important guidelines for the development of the concept of national security. In the course of scientific discussions on security issues, a modern broad and comprehensive understanding of national security has been adopted, consisting of three elements - the security of the individual, society and the state.

Ensuring security, ie creating a set of socio-economic, political, legal and other living conditions in which the individual would feel fully socially protected, is one of the most important conditions for the existence and development of the individual. The state of security of the individual is the most important criterion of democracy and civilization of modern society. It is a society acceptable to the individual, where well-functioning mechanisms of social protection of its interests, rights and freedoms are created. The

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problem of creating a sustainable society is directly related to the security of the individual, with the real possibilities of exercising his rights and freedoms.

The results of the analysis of scientific publications on this problem showed that researchers adhere to various worldviews and scientific positions, and science has not yet developed a common understanding. Some authors understand human rights as social opportunities to use basic goods (food, clothing, housing, normal recreation, education, personal integrity, etc.), which exist regardless of their state recognition. Other experts believe that human rights are social opportunities recognized by law, for the violation of which sanctions are applied by the state. In the first case, human rights are considered as a social category, and in the second - as a legal one. At the same time, despite the obvious connection between the phenomena of national security and human rights, there are very few scientific works devoted to their consideration.

The purpose of the article is to try to provide a philosophical justification for the correlation of the problem of national security with the problem of human rights.

Presenting main material. In the modern system of relations "individual - state" there are significant contradictions. On the one hand, the social transformation and political modernization of Ukrainian society, which began in the early 90's, put on the agenda a qualitatively new attitude of the state to the individual, its interests, rights and freedoms, creating an effective socio-political mechanism for personal security. . On the other hand, the individual is increasingly becoming hostage to the negative consequences of economic, socio-political, scientific, technical and other technologies of social development, ways of transforming social life, in which it is either a secondary object of attention and influence, or the subject of regular social experiments. and manipulations. The security of the individual must be ensured by political, economic and legal means and means. Unfortunately, the process of legal support of the individual's relationship with the state in Ukraine is far from complete, and in the context of armed conflict, reform and political modernization, this threatens the individual with many problems.

The process of formation and consolidation of human rights originates from the emergence of man as an individual and the formation of its holistic guidelines, which in itself determines the emergence of legal relations between the subjects, ie participants in such relations. Human history is a constant struggle for one's rights, from the natural ones that man is endowed with from birth to the right to free access to the Internet and the content distributed in its vastness. It is the struggle of man for his rights that often led to epoch-making changes in the socio-political life of different countries, which resulted in a rethinking of the place and role of man in relations with the state. It is in the context of globalization, new achievements that man seeks, endless search for new discoveries, the classification of human rights will only expand, which will lead to the need to create new mechanisms for their implementation and legal consolidation [1, p. 45].

In our opinion, human rights and freedoms should be understood as a set of socio-political, economic, ethical and other norms that determine the fundamentals of democratic and humanitarian status of the individual, his relationship with other people, society and the state [2].

Human rights are most closely linked to human security. According to the current UN classification [3], human rights in any country should be carried out in the following areas of its security: economic security, food security; health safety; environmental safety; personal security; public safety; political security.

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Human rights are regulated by law, ie fundamental human rights must be respected in any situation. They may be limited only by law and exclusively for the purposes specified in the Constitution of the country and in the most important international legal acts. It should be noted that in accordance with the Constitution of Ukraine, in the interests of national security, the following constitutional rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen may be restricted: the right to personal and family life (Article 32); the right to freedom of thought and speech, to the free expression of one's views and beliefs, the right to freely collect, store, use and disseminate information orally, in writing or otherwise - at one's own discretion (Article 34); the right to freedom of association in political parties and public organizations (Article 36); the right to assemble peacefully, without weapons and to hold meetings, rallies, marches and demonstrations (Article 36); the right to strike (Art. 44). As ensuring national security also includes combating crimes against its foundations, the following rights established in the Constitution of Ukraine may be limited in order to prevent them: the right to liberty and security of person (Article 29); the right to inviolability of the home (Article 30); the right to secrecy of correspondence, telephone conversations, telegraph and other correspondence (Article 31) [4]. The list of rights and freedoms to be restricted is commensurate with the international obligations of the state set out in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966, and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966. ., The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of 1950. A prerequisite for the restriction of constitutional rights and freedoms of man and citizen is that it can occur only on the basis and in cases specified by law, and usually by decision court. The procedural procedure for implementing such a restriction is enshrined in national law. Depending on the actual circumstances, state authorities, local self-government bodies, their officials and officials are authorized to choose ways to ensure national security on their own or through an appeal to a court. At the same time, as rightly noted by Yu. Irkha, the lack of proper control over their activities and imperfect procedure of bringing perpetrators to justice can lead to excessive restrictions on constitutional rights and freedoms of man and citizen and the associated serious consequences [5, p. 83].

Today, the recognition and effective observance of human rights is the most important criterion of national security, democracy and humanism in any country in the world. At the same time, the protection of human rights on an international scale (legitimate, approved by the world community) is not considered interference in the internal affairs of the country.

The category of "human rights" is largely defined by such concepts as "individual freedom", "human development", "individual security". The concept of individual freedom has become a widespread concept, especially in recent years. Although this term is actively used in public speeches by politicians of different orientations, there is no established definition of this concept in science yet.

Noting the different meaning given to the concept of "freedom", Sh.-L. Montesquieu wrote in his work "On the Spirit of Laws": "There is no word that has so many different meanings and would make such a different impression on the minds as the word "freedom". Some call freedom an easy opportunity to overthrow one who has been endowed with tyrannical power; others - the right to choose who they must obey; third - the right to bear arms and commit violence; fourth - see it in the privilege of being under the control of a person of their nationality or obey their own laws "[6, p. 288].

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Reflecting on the definition of freedom, Carl Jaspers noted: "Freedom is not an object. It does not have a real existence in the world that we, observing, could explore. Freedom as a subject of scientific knowledge does not exist. Therefore, freedom cannot be defined by a firmly established concept "[7, p. 170].

As you know, man is a social being, social, it depends on society and is formed by its social environment. On the other hand, it is no less obvious that man is a natural being. As a "human natural being", the individual is endowed with consciousness and will, which determine its ability to resist nature and influence it. Hence the most important characteristic of man - his relative autonomy as an individual in relation to nature and society.

In this regard, we can and should talk about two aspects of understanding human freedom: natural, which is the uncontrolled implementation of innate instincts and behavioral programs, and social or civil freedom, within some conscious limitations in the implementation of these programs, if they contradict the accepted norms of behavior in the existing society. Directions for improving these freedoms are opposite: the perfection of natural freedom lies in its infinity, the perfection of civil liberty - in its conscious limitation, based on the interests of society.

As long as man did not realize himself as a free being, he was outside politics, perceiving the power existing over him as something natural and necessary, having the force of divine or natural law. Politics comes into people's lives only with a sense of personal freedom, in its acquisition.

The modern understanding of human rights by the world community is articulated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the United Nations in December 1948, as well as in a number of other UN instruments incorporated in the International Bill of Human Rights. The bill includes such documents as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966), and others. The European Convention on Human Rights (1950) is also of paramount importance.

In 1990, the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) introduced the concept of "human development" [8]. According to the UNDP concept, human development is a process of expanding freedom of choice. It is emphasized that the number of choices can be infinite. However, at all levels of development, the three most important options are to be able to choose a long and healthy life, gain knowledge and have access to the resources needed to maintain a decent standard of living [3]. The Concept itself is based on four basic principles:

- Productivity - the ability to achieve the desired effect of their activities and increase it, to fully participate in the process of income generation and work for a monetary reward. Therefore, economic growth is one of the components of human development models;

- Equality as a priori equal opportunities for people. All barriers to economic and political life must be removed;

- resilience - access to opportunities not only for current but also for future generations;

- capacity building, which implies that development is carried out by people's efforts, not just in the interests of the people. They must constantly expand their participation in the decision-making process, as well as in other processes that determine their lives.

The concept of human development defines human security as the ability to freely exercise the right to choose in conditions of freedom and in the absence of danger, as well as full confidence that these opportunities will continue in the future.

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Considering the problem of human rights and freedoms, it is necessary to briefly dwell on its understanding in Ukraine. The Soviet period of Ukrainian history left a significant imprint on both the understanding of security in general and the understanding of rights and freedoms in particular. The Stalinist and Brezhnev constitutions showed a clear priority of socio-economic (that is, national) rights over those that are considered natural and inalienable (that is, the rights of a particular person). Formally enshrining a number of political rights (freedom of speech, press, assembly and rallies, street marches and demonstrations), the 1936 Constitution stipulated the possibility of their use "in accordance with the interests of workers." Some of the human rights in this Constitution were completely absent, even formally (for example, freedom of movement, not to mention the right to private property). The main emphasis was not on the space of human freedom, but on the "guardianship of the state." Liberal values (freedom, independence, individualism and universalism, market economy, freedom within the law), hostile to the Soviet state, were not mentioned even at the level of the declaration.

The Constitution of 1936 provided for the right of citizens to work, ie "the right to receive guaranteed work with payment for their work in accordance with its quantity and quality", the right to rest, the right to material security in old age and in case of illness and disability, the right to education. The USSR Constitution of 1977 supplemented the list of proclaimed social rights of citizens, adding to them such as the right to health care, the right to housing, the right to use cultural achievements, as well as guaranteeing freedom of scientific, technical and artistic creativity.

The 1996 Constitution of Ukraine established the system of power relations that had actually developed at that time: a semi-presidential unitary republic with a parliament de facto devoid of control, a relatively weak judiciary, and a government without significant political functions and therefore constantly dependent on direct presidential support. In general, the irresponsibility of the state to society in the new Constitution of Ukraine remained almost at the level of Soviet times. The constitutional system of human rights protection does not actually work.

The second section of the Constitution of Ukraine "Rights, Freedoms and Duties of Man and Citizen", which accounts for almost a third of the total number of constitutional norms, contains a large number of direct borrowings from two well-known UN international human rights pacts of 1966, but in purely legally does not distinguish between the provisions of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, which the state must comply with under any circumstances, and the provisions of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, the possibility of which is associated with the real economic situation. or another country. The point is that socio-economic rights are usually considered norms of direct action only in the presence of special official comments, which determine the specific parameters of judicial protection of the so-called "positive", ie existing due to state activity, rights and freedoms [8, 9, 12, 19].

It should also be noted that the 1950 European Convention [10] deals with "human rights and fundamental freedoms", and the 1996 Constitution of Ukraine deals only with "human rights and freedoms". This means that the constitutional protection of such subjects of rights as legal entities is not provided.

In the context of globalization, a number of changes are taking place in ensuring human security and restricting human rights [11-12]. This is a sharp increase in the dependence of people's living standards on the interests of multinational companies; reducing the importance of the factor of territorial conditionality, which means that changes in human

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life more and more often depend on the processes occurring far from its location; reducing the role of national borders, which lose their significance not only for trade, capital and information, but also for ideas, moral norms, national culture and values; increasing rates of change in markets and technologies, which contributes to accelerating the pace of life and increasing the level of instability in society.

Thus, human rights in a concentrated form express the basic vital interests of the individual in the modern form. One of the basic human rights and freedoms is the right to inviolability of his personal (private) life. In this area, there are certain contradictions between the individual and society (state). On the one hand, from the standpoint of national security, society and the state want to have a certain (and, as much as possible) amount of information about a person. On the other hand, a person as an individual and a thinking being has the right to a certain amount of personal information that is available only to him. In other words, in order to ensure its security, the state wants to know as much as possible about each of its citizens, while a person tries to give the state only the most necessary (defined in regulations) minimum information about himself, and only with his consent. As for violations of human rights to privacy, they can be represented as follows:

- violent violation of the privacy of an individual or interference in his personal affairs (eavesdropping and interception of telephone conversations, Internet messages, perustration of correspondence, etc.);

- Publication of personal information about a person, which, from the point of view of this person, adversely affects his social image or causes him pain and mental suffering (even in cases where the information disseminated is true);

- exposing a person in a false light in the eyes of others without his consent;

- the use of a person's name or image in the interests of the person using it.

The category "private life" in principle has no legal meaning; legal regulation only establishes the limits of its inviolability ("privacy") and, accordingly, the limits of permissible interference. It is no coincidence that the right to privacy is defined in some legal systems as "the right to be granted to oneself."

Today, the right to privacy is attracting increasing public attention. It is included in the catalog of human rights and enshrined in many constitutions of democratic countries. The idea of legislative protection of privacy acquires a new, deeper meaning.

The problem of regulating the process of collecting personal data, storing information and other related issues related to the work with personal data in our country (and, consequently, to ensuring privacy) is now relatively resolved and known to a wide range of lawyers. Obviously, the legislation is not perfect and needs to be improved, but the main provisions are regulated by the Law of Ukraine "On Personal Data Protection" [13]. Thus, in accordance with Art. 12 of this Law, the collection of personal data is part of the process of their processing, which involves actions to select or organize information about an individual. The personal data subject shall be informed about the owner of personal data, the composition and content of the collected personal data, his rights defined by this Law, the purpose of personal data collection and the persons to whom his personal data are transferred:

- at the time of personal data collection, if personal data are collected from the personal data subject;

- in other cases within thirty working days from the date of personal data collection.

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In addition to the above Law, legal entities and individuals have the opportunity to address issues related to their own information security, using the provisions of the Civil Code of Ukraine, the Law of Ukraine "On Information" and other legislation of Ukraine.

However, the real situation is very different from the regulatory model. Unauthorized wiretapping and other violations of the privacy of individuals are often reported in the media. Moreover, proposals to create a national population register - a centralized database, which would accumulate almost comprehensive information about the individual - have been repeatedly made public. Despite the fact that this was justified by the fact that it would be more convenient for both the state and the individual, this idea did not receive support among the general population of Ukraine.

Every country needs laws - clear and detailed, which contain guarantees against unauthorized interference in private life by public and private organizations, and in cases where such interference is objectively necessary and sanctioned by law - mandatory procedures that would eliminate arbitrariness in the exercise of their powers.

The right to privacy cannot but be subject to certain restrictions, and such restrictions are objectively necessary to ensure the interests of the vast majority of the country's population, who, by definition, express "public interest" in relation to a small part of the population engaged in illegal activities. . This primarily applies to antisocial individuals - thieves, economic criminals, members of organized crime and mafia groups, as well as terrorist organizations.

In general, intrusion into the private life of an individual can be carried out in different ways: by the state and its structures; by individual social, national, etc. groups; and, ultimately, by individuals. The inviolability of the personality of almost any person is the most vulnerable in the information sphere. The Doctrine of Information Security of Ukraine states that the vital interests of a person in the information sphere are [14]:

- ensuring constitutional human rights and freedoms to collect, store, use and disseminate information;
- ensuring the constitutional human rights to the protection of privacy;
- Protection from destructive information and psychological influences.

In addition, the Laws of Ukraine "On Information" [15] and "On State Secrets" [16] are the means of ensuring privacy. However, the question of what information should be considered open and what should be closed, and what should be the responsibility for the disclosure of official or commercial information, is still not finally resolved, as there is no relevant legal framework.

It can be argued that information influences that threaten to destabilize, destructive, and harm the interests of the individual, society and the state should be considered dangerous for the observance of human rights and freedoms. Since the complete absence of threats (including in the information sphere) is an unattainable ideal for our dangerous world, human security is determined by the ability to prevent, repel, neutralize dangerous information influences.

The problem of security and the problem of respect for human rights and freedoms are often in contradiction with each other. For example, D. Smiley points out that "some liberals, progressives and democrats recognize, at least intuitively, that" national security "is a code word for tribalism, while" human rights "is a code word for the rule of law." [17]. The origins of this contradiction lie in the conflict between the inclinations, rights and interests of individuals and their associations, on the one hand, and the interests of the great human communities of which they are a part, on the other. In a broader sense, it is a

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contradiction between the interests of the minority and the majority. And since security is usually primarily concerned with the interests of the majority of society, restricting the rights and freedoms of a minority whose interests and activities (or those of many members) sometimes pose a real or potential danger to society is justified [18-20]. .

Security threats in one way or another arise as a result of criminal or other activities threatening the national interests, carried out by various organizations, social groups, corporate associations and other groups organized to meet certain interests, directed (in whole or in part) against the interests of the individual, society and society. states. Therefore, people who belong to such associations are under suspicion, although their guilt is not always obvious, and in many cases they do not participate and are not responsible for the anti-government and anti-social activities of the communities to which they belong. In this regard, in all democracies, the solution of problems of prevention and leveling of threats to national security in various spheres, as well as security in general, is carried out taking into account the extent to which measures are adequate to existing threats and combined with constitutional requirements for human rights and freedoms. and citizen. The constant raising and discussion of this issue in many countries, including Ukraine, is especially actively initiated by human rights organizations. This is due to the fact that security (and it is often not about the security of the individual, but about the security of society) can not be provided in many cases without some restriction of the rights and freedoms of individuals and even socio-ethnic groups (including their right to free movement and choice of residence).

It should be noted here that the generalized principles of human rights restrictions are established by international norms. In particular, Art. 29 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights declares that in the exercise of his rights and freedoms everyone is subject only to such restrictions as are prescribed by law solely to ensure the dignified recognition and respect for the rights and freedoms of others and to meet the just morals of public order. democratic society [21]. According to Art. 10 of the European Convention on Human Rights, which establishes restrictions on the right to express one's opinion, such restrictions must be [10]: 1) established by law; 2) be necessary in a democratic society; in the interests of national security, territorial integrity or public security, to prevent riots or crimes, to protect health or morals, to protect the reputation or rights of others, to prevent the disclosure of confidential information or to uphold the authority and impartiality of the court. Similar restrictions are imposed on certain rights and freedoms. At the same time, for example, under the "necessity of a democratic society" the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR judgment of 24.03.1988, paragraph 67) explains that any interference (restriction) in the implementation of the law must meet the "urgent public need". [22]. It should be noted that the above international legal requirements with minor differences are embodied in Part 3 of Art. 34 of the Constitution of Ukraine, which establishes the right of everyone to freedom of thought and speech, to free expression of their views and beliefs and the right to information. These constitutional provisions due to the lack of a generalizing norm can be formally extrapolated to determine the legitimate purpose of restricting other constitutional rights and freedoms [23, p. 129].

With regard to the individual, ensuring his or her personal and collective security in society (of course, together with this very society, of which he or she is an integral part) must in itself be regarded as one of the most important human rights. Although this is not explicitly enshrined in international human rights instruments, the analysis of these instruments, in particular such fundamental ones as the Universal Declaration of Human

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Rights [21], the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights [24] and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, political rights [25] - indicates that this is so. These acts include, inter alia, human rights and freedoms, such as the right to life, liberty and security of person; the right to the free development of her personal rights in the economic, social and cultural spheres; the right to fair and favorable working conditions; the right to an adequate standard of living for herself and her family, including adequate food, clothing and shelter, and a steady improvement in living conditions; the right to the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health, etc.

A comparison of these and many other rights enshrined in these and other international human rights instruments with the areas of national security in various fields of activity shows that the main purpose and areas of security are precisely the creation of the minimum necessary (ie, primarily safe) conditions for the exercise of these rights.

The existence of this contradiction between the need to ensure security as a predominantly collective law and individual human rights and freedoms, the contradiction between the need to ensure the rights of majorities and minorities, individuals and the rest of society is essentially recognized in these international instruments. In order to be able to at least partially resolve this contradiction, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights includes the provision that "in exercising their rights and freedoms, everyone should be subject only to such restrictions as are prescribed by law solely to ensure the proper recognition and respect of the rights and freedoms of others. observance of just requirements of morality, public order and general well-being in a democratic society "(Article 29) [21]. In order to develop this provision, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights has established as grounds for the application of these restrictions "the protection of national security, public order, health, morals or the rights and freedoms of others" (Article 12) [25]. Many of these rules are reflected with various variations in the constitutions of most democracies, including the Constitution of Ukraine.

Politicians and political scientists, who interpret democracy as subordination to a minority of the majority, believe that security is primarily concerned with the interests of the majority of society. Therefore, as noted above, the restriction of the rights and freedoms of a minority whose interests, values and goals may pose a real or potential danger to society is justified. Proponents of the latest conceptions of democracy, who see it as a defining criterion for protecting the rights of minorities and individuals, believe that such considerations are intended to justify undemocratic policies of governments that commit blatant violations of human rights and freedoms under the pretext of national security.

In this regard, international human rights organizations have been sharply criticized by those democracies that initially cared about human rights, but after September 11, 2001, abruptly changed their orientation and took emergency measures to combat terrorism.

Conclusions. Human rights and national security are closely interlinked and complementary. In democracies, national security means, above all, a means of ensuring civil peace and the personal rights of citizens. Both are necessary for the long-term stability and prosperity of the country. Free and democratic states that respect the rights of their citizens help to lay the foundations for international peace. On the contrary, states that grossly and systematically violate human rights often begin to pose a threat to neighboring countries and the international community.

In Ukraine, as in most countries of the world, the category of "national security" covers a wide range of issues in various spheres of public life. We fully agree with the point of view of Yu. Irkha that this allows us to interpret its content too broadly and, as a result, to

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operate it arbitrarily in restricting human and civil rights and freedoms and in punishing those who threaten it with their statements or actions. In addition, the field of national security is extremely difficult to reform and control, because for objective reasons, information about the real situation in the state and society has a very limited number of people [5, p. 81].

The real interdependence of the phenomena of national security and human rights is often contradictory. Often the origins of this contradiction lie in the division between the interests, values and goals of individuals and their associations, on the one hand, and the interests of the great human communities of which they are a part, on the other.

Today, the rights and freedoms of the individual are one of the most important objects of national security policy. By fixing real protection and guaranteeing the rights and freedoms of the individual in a particular community, human rights can act as a humanistic guideline for the development not only of the state as a whole, but also of the national security system that has developed in the country. At the same time, the problem of the interdependence of national security and human rights is not a problem of choice on the principle of "either / or". This is a problem of compromise between ensuring national security and respect for human rights, between the realization of human rights and the protection of national security.

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